

Implementation of Augmented and Virtual Reality in Crucial Domains : Benefiting the Differently Abled and Elderly

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Abstract— The integration of Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) technologies into various domains has ushered in a new era of innovative and transformative practices. This research paper explores the burgeoning landscape of AR and VR applications within the predominant sectors such as Education, Healthcare and more targeting the differently abled people.

Keywords—*Mobility and Physical Assistance, Education, Learning Platforms and Models*

I. MOBILITY AND AUTONOMY

Electric-powered wheelchairs (EPW) are assistive devices that help the mobility of people with motor disabilities. The well-proclaimed motion guide has some flaws that might undermine its purpose. EPW users have constantly reported that it is difficult to handle the equipment, especially when driving alone. In the 90s, many proposed the initiation of EPW driving simulators to help people understand the environment and the equipment itself. The developers and designers can even iterate on their EPW to increase its utility and reduce defects. A 3D simulator for driving EPWs is the ViEW platform (Virtual Electric Wheelchair), created by the French laboratory LCOMS. The platform uses augmented reality to improve the immersion in the driving tests in tele-rehabilitation. Rehabilitation services over telecommunication networks/internet are called "tele-rehabilitation" or "e-rehabilitation". E. L. M. Naves et.al, believe that this system provides effective solutions [1] compared to traditional ones. "Smart cities" are to drive economic growth and improve the quality of life of people. The design must allow the inclusion of all kinds of citizens. The inclusion of RFID and IoT in AR enables wheelchair users to reach items beyond their arm's length, thereby extending their limits of independence in everyday activities [2]. A robotic system offers increased control functionality to disabled people by equipping MANUS (robotic arm) with EPW. Many proposed different interaction possibilities for wheelchairs user by gestures. The gesture recognition works using the Kinect camera installed in the designated/desired system. Rashid et.al wanted to provide personal autonomy to wheelchair users by allowing them to shop independently. In a study conducted with the help of Vigatans public residents in Barcelona, the effectiveness of the system based on gender and age had a great outcome.

II. A FOCUS ON COGNITIVE AND BEHAVIORAL FUNCTIONING

In psychiatry and neuropsychology, the contribution of AR/VR is overwhelming. The ultimate objective is to understand the cognitive and behavioral functioning of people [3]. This session model helps the participants improve attention, memory and other intellectual activities such as inductive and deductive reasoning. The clinical logic supports using Augmented and Virtual reality in psychotherapy and is now well established. Controlled studies that provide convincing results on clinical performance are few due to the lack of standard VR systems. Autism is a profound disorder that one in 160 children suffer from it. People with Autism face daily challenges such as social interactions, especially non-verbal communication. The aim is to develop a virtual setting to learn how to perceive emotions [4], and Anna Schwarze et.al intends to progress it. The Virtual Reality environment builds use any real-time development platform such as Unity or Unreal Engine 4. Then the VR session is put to the test by following the case design, which will give detailed reports about the session itself. The data collection used in this environment is a set of Virtual emotion cards that emphasize every human reaction to varying situations. The participants of the session access the emotion cards using HTC Vive controllers to submit them in each domain name, such as happy, sad etc. The response to the test submissions uses visual and auditory feedback. The developers introduced a scoring system so that the players measure themselves against themselves. The test sessions showed excellent participation counts (65 overall points in the first session - 134 overall points in the second session). The ARSFM learning system facilitated social skill training for adolescents with ASD [5]. With the help of the Autism Association in Taiwan, Chien-Hsu Chen et.al has recruited three adolescent participants with a net Intelligence Quotient (IQ) of more than 85. The method undertaken is not constructive for cognitive development since all the participants were fluent in Mandarin and Taiwanese. This test AR system uses an augmented mirror through which participants can view their virtual 3D expressions and gain hands-on experience. The test period had many shifts, one being the demonstration of stimulus control, a compulsive study. A follow-up phase showed that the recruits raised their score from the 20 percentiles to a maximum score of 96.43%. The performance difference between the baseline phase and the follow-up was drastic.

III. BRIDGING COMPLEXITY IN HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTIONS

Intellectual and multiple disabilities brew complexity to the HCI (Human-Computer Interaction) community. The creation of design interfaces and applications for those individuals is a requirement [6]. The Systematic Literature Review (SLR) is conducted based on definite guidelines, and three answers are in demand. Based on the research questions, the PICOC method defines the scope. The SLR report gives us the types of studies possible and what disabilities require the help of AR/VR. Evaluation and data analysis measures the participant's performance and effectiveness of treatments, respectively. The reports show 61% of therapy are effective, a substantial number for a rising technology.

Rian Dutra da Cunha et.al, emphasizes that intensive studies in AR/VR will be an effective solution. AR is the answer to help individuals with special needs and enable the development of their daily way of living [7]. A total of 119 individuals with different disabilities helped in the study under the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis) guidelines, and the results were significant. The selected candidates ensure to meet the eligibility criteria to establish safety. The role of mixed reality and specific training methods in developing independence among individuals with disabilities is enhanced. Reem Sulaiman Baragash et.al acknowledged that the assessment has an average score of 2.20 out of 3.00 and a maximum of 2.50.

IV. AR AND VR IN INCLUSIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

Education is pivotal to all. But those with complications must approach in creative ways to understand the concepts. Virtual technologies increase students' engagement and allow a constructive approach to learning [8]. Complex devices are not a requirement, and students can access VR content on online platforms such as YouTube. VR systems help test the usefulness and accessibility of products/environments beforehand, thereby reducing cost and effort consumption. A basic understanding of math is mandatory to have independence in society. But those with disabilities need a unique curriculum and methodology to understand. Ryan O. Kellems et.al partnered with Mr Kramer to study the use of AR teaching strategy [9]. Mr Kramer is a resource math teacher who has a class of 25 students with learning disability. The team discovered that the batch liked to play a game on their iPad called Pokémon, an AR-based video game.

Then each student's behavior is monitored and noted to develop an AR-based application to learn mathematics. Newman, a student, used the app to grasp the problem and its solution. Newman's performance in class increased after using AR instructional and teaching strategies. Students can benefit from such educational models and exhibit their own experiences with a constructive approach to different scenarios (outside the school curriculum). The design-based research adaptation helps obtain objective and in-depth information using qualitative and quantitative data [10]. The

real-time experience provided by AR helps students observe their surroundings and react accordingly. A teaching application using AR, an eight-week program to promote and study the outcome of such a model, resulted in absolute success. The faculty set for the program noticed students latch on to the sessions (90 minutes) conducted every day. The statistics show that the student's attention time has increased drastically; SK, a student with a moderate mental disability, has increased his attention time from 41% to 100%.

V. EMPOWERING EDUCATION

Chien-Yu Lin et.al worked with Aurasma, an AR-based mobile application available both on android and iOS. The application offers a medical illustration channel for free. The content provided is of two parts, the Chinese Tangram puzzle and the square puzzle. The experiment has six games, and the participants must solve them with the help of Aurasma (not the proctor), then the points are noted. The participants have attained significant achievements via Aurasma augmented reality instead of only operating via paper [11]. 90.5% of participants strongly agree the experiment content is abundant, 9.5% of participants agree the experiment content is copious, and they all stand on the positive responses. 95.2% of participants were satisfied strongly with this experiment included 4.8% of participants were satisfied. 95.2% of participants strongly agree that operative technology could help in education.

AR and VR implemented in special education needs have made radical changes to society. Hasan Köse et.al believed students with disabilities gain advantages by following such systems. The learning materials are analyzed using descriptive content analysis. A few databases used in the system were MEDLINE Complete, ScienceDirect, Scopus and Social Sciences Citation Index etc. Goblin XNA is an open-source research environment used to develop the user interfaces for the modules. The inclusion of games, social stories and video models increases the effectiveness points. The system is not implemented full scale but will be in a decade [12].

VI. PRACTICAL MODELS AND APPLICATIONS

Our environment is complex to understand also reconstructing it stands difficult. By using AR/VR, children and confined people know their surroundings [13]. A virtual zoo is projected anywhere with a mobile screen and a printed marker. The application utilizes Unity 3D and Cinema 4D, which increases immersion and interface. The "marker" helps the device place virtual objects on it and can be any image type developed in graphic design software. There are a total of 6 scenes, each holding one animal. Then the questions are raised for each set by loading an XML file. The game went through various tests with the help of a group of five kids. The kids latched on to the teaching method, learnt questions and answers for each animal in the scene, and attained long-term knowledge about animals. Remedial students face difficulties during reading sessions. Augmented Reality is a new educational tool used to create storybooks for those exceptional students [14]. A physical

book is said to have five considerable limitations, so the chance of wielding a Reality book has a reasonable percentage. First, the behavior is studied using observation, interview and reading sessions. The Cognitive load theory (CLT) is a foundation to design and develop AR Flashcards for the system. The AR Baca-Pulih flashcard and Hafiza Abas et.al intends to prove that AR storybooks can improve the way of learning for students.

Hijaiyah letters are in the Al Qur'an, consisting of 28 letters, emphasizing consonant sounds. Children with mild mental retardation and low IQ who wish to read the Holy book can now read with ease. Irawan Afrianto et.al conducted the research by dividing it into four stages. A widely used technique to help those special children concede letters is the Gillingham Method. It uses a visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, and tactile (VAKT) approach for teaching the desired content/language. The markers scan the letters and produce them in a 3D model, projecting them into the AR application. Data storage in this application uses PlayerPrefs. Children who have difficulty concentrating have increased by 12%, while for children who easily concentrate, there is a 6% increase in Hijaiyah letter learning [15].

VII. ENHANCING ACCESSIBILITY FOR THE ELDERLY AND DISABLED

The elderly and disabled face problems even in their homes. The Integration of Augmented reality and Smart Home control is a great solution [16]. The physical actions are fed into the X10 devices and stored as an XML file. After scanning the QR code of a commodity, the system accesses the Web to retrieve a unique ID. Then the X10 device and server interact to review the status of each XML file. Then the products manuals and states are delivered to the user for further operations. The SOA (Service Oriented Architecture) approach fitted the system. Test results show that 40% agree that people can adapt to this system.

Cloud computing involves delivering hosted services over the internet. AR-based courseware exhausts mobile devices' capacity, thereby decreasing efficiency [17]. To solve that problem, we introduce cloud computing as it offers vast storage capacity. The quality of wireless communication is a crucial factor for such systems. Within the Ministry of Education, ETP focuses on developing and promoting this educational technology as they have acknowledged the favorable results achieved by Malaysian schools. Ab Aziz et.al believed that cloud computing provides AR-based education at low cost, consolidates management of programs, and better resources/content usage.

Developing an AR model for people with low vision and hearing is complicated [18]. The letters and numbers recognition on the template will be using an artificial neural network. Then addressed to the user. As for hearing, the sound of each word is understood by the neural network, later activating the appropriate neurons. This approach makes it possible to use computer resources effectively and reduce the volume of memory used. Volodymyr Hrytsyk et.al state that the system generates the notion of whether

identifiable objects are the treatment frame of video or voice recording as a speaker.

VIII. ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND HEALTHCARE

The Influence of ICT (Information and communications technology) is high. Adaptive physical education and activities using VR technology have emerged. There is a considerable need for disabled people to participate in sports and other physical activities [19]. "Besides textbooks and dioceses, adaptive physical education requires actual escapades", stated by Sunyoung Kang et.al. The education system offers a low risk of injury and repetitive training. VR sports classrooms are now part of the training methodology in Korea. National Sports Promotion Foundation supported the initiation. Then the AI got grafted into the system to increase the productivity of the sessions. Rising innovations in the technology of AR/VR are positive. A VR flight simulation was developed especially for those who fear flying, and a VR classroom to detect ADHD (attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder) in children. SeeingVR, a research toolkit, is used for making VR accessible to people with low vision. A workshop in 2012 at the ACM Intelligent User Interface conference spread the awareness of AR/VR in the field of medical care and education [20]. The European Commission, considering the perspective, funded the AR/VR based projects for the workshop panel.

CONCLUSIONS

AR and VR have the potential to bridge physical limitations by offering immersive experiences and real-time information overlays. In healthcare, these technologies can facilitate rehabilitation, pain management, and remote monitoring, enabling elderly and differently-abled individuals to regain independence and better manage their conditions. Education with AR and VR can create inclusive learning environments, making education more accessible to all, regardless of physical or cognitive impairments.

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